

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF SHORT-FIBER COMPOSITES

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Summary

The equivalent inclusion method is proposed to solve steady-state heat conduction problems in composites. This method is analogous to the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method in elasticity. Then, the thermal conductivities of aligned and misoriented short-fiber composites are obtained based on the equivalent inclusion method. Finally, the validity of the present method is discussed by comparing it with the other models.

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1. Introduction

Short-fiber composites have been used extensively in a number of industrial applications mainly as a structural material owing to its ease of fabrication and relatively low cost. Most short fibers, however, are misoriented either two-dimensionally or three-dimensionally. Recently, there is a growing demand for short-fiber composites in some new application areas such as electronics devices. Then, a complete understanding of the thermo-physical properties of short-fiber composites becomes a prerequisite for a composite designer to apply it. In this paper, an emphasis is placed upon the prediction of the thermal conductivity of a short-fiber composite which includes from particulate to misoriented short-fiber type.

A number of analytical models have been proposed to predict the effective thermal conductivity of a short-fiber composite (1-11). These models were focused on either aligned short-fiber composites (1-8), including particulate composites, or completely random short-fiber composites (9-11). The latter models, however, used a laminated plate type scheme to account for different fiber orientation; hence, they cannot account for the correct interaction between various fibers that are misoriented. On the other hand, we have recently proposed a new method to solve steady-state heat conduction problems in composites, which is called "equivalent inclusion method" (12). The equivalent inclusion method in steady-state heat conduction problems is analogous to Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method in elasticity problems (13). Hence, the equivalent inclusion method in steady-state heat conduction requires only algebraic operations. Then, we have applied the equivalent inclusion method to the case of a misoriented short-fiber composite (14) where the interaction between various fibers with different orientation angles is taken into account correctly.

This paper is intended to overview analytical models for the prediction of the thermal conductivity of a short-fiber composite and discuss the validity of the equivalent inclusion method by comparing it with bounded solutions (7,11) and self-consistent method. To this end, we first review the equivalent inclusion method in Section 2 where the cases of both isotropic and anisotropic matrix are stated and also the formulation for a mis-oriented short-fiber is briefly reviewed. Then, the numerical results based on several models are presented for a particulate and a misoriented short-fiber composite in Section 4. Finally, conclusion is given in Section 5.

2. Equivalent Inclusion Method

2.1. Isotropic Matrix

Let us consider the case in which a single ellipsoidal inhomogeneity (domain Ω) with thermal conductivity K_{ij}^f is embedded in an infinite isotropic body D of conductivity K_{ij}^m and constant heat flux q_i^0 is applied at far field as shown in Figure 1(a), where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker's delta. The index operation will be used throughout this paper unless otherwise noted. In the equivalent inclusion method, the inhomogeneity Ω is converted to an inclusion Ω filled by a uniformly distributed doublet (Figure 1(b)). The equivalence between Figure 1(a) and (b) requires, in Ω

$$K_{ij}^m \delta_{ij} (T_{,j}^O + T_{,j}^O - T_{,j}^*) = K_{ij}^f (T_{,j}^O + T_{,j}^C) \quad (1)$$

where a comma followed by j denotes $\partial/\partial x_j$, the left-hand side equation stands for the heat flux of the equivalent inclusion (Figure 1(b)) and the right-hand side for the actual inhomogeneity (Figure 1(a)). In Eq. (1),

Figure 1 -Theoretical model: an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity (Ω) with K_{ij}^f embedded in an infinite matrix(a) converted to an equivalent inclusion (Ω) with uniform doublet distribution D_i (b)

Figure 2 - The model for a misoriented short fiber composite (a), definition of the local axis x_3' and global coordinate system x_1 (b) and unit sphere describing the orientation of a fiber OP (c)

$T_{,j}^0$ is the uniform thermal gradient and is related to the far field applied heat flux $q_{,i}^0$ by

$$T_{,i}^0 = -q_{,i}^0 / K^m. \quad (2)$$

$T_{,i}^c$ is the thermal gradient disturbed by the existence of the inhomogeneity and $T_{,i}^*$ is the so-called "eigen thermal gradient" corresponding to the uniformly distributed doublet (15). $T_{,i}^*$ has some constant value in Ω , but vanishes outside Ω , $T_{,i}^c$ is related to $T_{,i}^*$ as (12)

$$T_{,i}^c = S_{ij} T_{,j}^* \quad (3)$$

where S_{ij} is called "S" tensor and depends only on the shape of the ellipsoidal inhomogeneity. The explicit expression of S_{ij} for several types of ellipsoid are given in Appendix A. From Eqs. (1) and (3), we can solve for $T_{,i}^*$ which can be expressed in terms of $T_{,i}^0$. Thus, the key equations in the equivalent inclusion method are Eqs. (1) and (3) which have the same structure as in the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method (13) with a complete correspondence of variables between in heat conduction (the present problem) and elasticity (Table I).

Table I.

Elasticity	Heat Conduction
Stiffness C_{ijkl}	Thermal conductivity K_{ij}
Stress σ_{ij}	Heat flux $q_{,i}$
Strain e_{ij}	Temperature gradient $T_{,i}$

2.2. Anisotropic Matrix

In an anisotropic media, the differential equation of steady-state heat conduction due to a unit point source at a point \underline{x}' is given by

$$K_1 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_1^2} + K_2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_2^2} + K_3 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_3^2} + \delta(\underline{x} - \underline{x}') = 0 \quad (4)$$

where x_i coordinates are taken to coincide with axes of the principal thermal conductivity K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 . We make the following transformation from x_i to y_i ,

$$y_i = (K/K_I)^{1/2} x_i \quad (5)$$

where K may be chosen arbitrary. Then, Eq. (4) is reduced to

$$\sqrt{\frac{K_1 K_2 K_3}{K}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y_3^2} \right) + \delta(\underline{y} - \underline{y}') = 0 \quad (6)$$

which is the equation for the isotropic media. Thus, the problem of anisotropic media can be converted to the isotropic problem if the conductivity of matrix (K_{ij}^{mv}) and inhomogeneity $\Omega(K_{ij}^f)$ in y coordinate are defined by (15)

$$K_{ij}^{my} = \sqrt{\frac{K_1 K_2 K_3}{K}} \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

$$K_{ij}^{fy} = \sqrt{\frac{K_1 K_2 K_3}{K K_1 K_J}} K_{ij}^f \quad (8)$$

In the above equations (Eqs. (5) and (8)), the upper case indices (I and J) take the same integer value as the lower case ones (i and j), but they are not to be summed.

Now consider the equivalence condition in y_i coordinates,

$$K_{ij}^{my}(T_{,j}^{oy} + T_{,j}^{cy} - T_{,j}^{*y}) = K_{ij}^{fy}(T_{,j}^{oy} + T_{,j}^{cy}) \quad (9)$$

and

$$T_{,i}^{cy} = S_{ij}^y T_{,j}^{*y} \quad (10)$$

where superscript y denotes the quantity referred to as y_i coordinates. Note that S_{ij}^y is easily obtainable since the matrix is regarded as isotropic media. By use of Eq. (5), we have

$$T_{,i}^y = \frac{\partial T^y}{\partial y_i} = \sqrt{\frac{K_I}{K}} T_{,i} \quad (11)$$

A substitution of Eqs. (7), (8) and (11) into Eqs. (9) and (10) yields the following equivalency condition referred to as x_i coordinates,

$$K_I(T_{,i}^o + T_{,i}^c - T_{,i}^*) = K_{ij}^f(T_{,i}^o + T_{,i}^c) \quad (12)$$

and

$$T_{,i}^c = \sqrt{\frac{K_J}{K_I}} S_{ij}^y T_{,j}^* \quad (13)$$

Eqs. (12) and (13) indicate that S tensor for anisotropic media S_{ij}^A can be related to S tensor for isotropic median S_{ij}^y by

$$S_{ij}^A = \sqrt{\frac{K_J}{K_I}} S_{ij}^y \quad (14)$$

Eq. (14) suggests that we may simply adopt the following replacement in isotropic S tensor given in Appendix A

$$a_i \rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{K}{K_I}} a_i \quad (15)$$

Thus, with S_{ij}^y the inhomogeneity problem in anisotropic media can be treated as that in isotropic media, in the same manner as described in the previous section. When the axes of anisotropy and ellipsoid do not coincide in determining S_{ij}^A , we must find the length and direction of the principal axes of ellipsoid in y_i space.

2.3. Multiple Inhomogeneities

The above formulation for a single ellipsoidal inhomogeneity has been extended to the case where numerous ellipsoidal inhomogeneities are embedded

in the matrix, thus the interaction between the inhomogeneities becomes important (12). Let us introduce the average disturbance of the temperature gradient in the matrix (which may be called "interaction term"), defined by

$$\tilde{T}_{,j} = \frac{1}{V_{D-\Omega}} \int_{D-\Omega} (T_{,j}^t - T_{,j}^o) dv \quad (16)$$

where T^t is the total (actual) temperature and $V_{D-\Omega}$ is the volume of the matrix.

Then the equivalent inclusion method yields

$$\begin{aligned} q_i^o + q_i &= K_{ij}^m (T_{,j}^o + \tilde{T}_{,j} + T_{,j}^c - T_{,j}^*) \\ &= K_{ij}^f (T_{,j}^o + \tilde{T}_{,j} + T_{,j}^c) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where q_i and $T_{,j}^c$ are the disturbance of the heat flux and the temperature gradient due to a representative inhomogeneity, respectively. The disturbance of the heat flux q_i when integrated over the entire domain D vanishes (12),

$$\int_D q_i dv = 0. \quad (18)$$

From Eqs. (16)-(18), we obtain

$$\tilde{T}_{,i} = -\frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} (T_{,i}^c - T_{,i}^*) dv \quad (19)$$

where V_D is the volume of the entire domain D . For the case of an aligned short-fiber composite, $T_{,i}^c$ and $T_{,i}^*$ are constant, hence Eq. (7) is reduced to

$$\tilde{T}_{,i} = -f(T_{,i}^c - T_{,i}^*) \quad (20)$$

where f is the volume fraction of fibers and it should be noted that the intersection term $\tilde{T}_{,i}$ vanishes for $f = 0$.

2.4. Thermal Conductivity

In order to compute the effective thermal conductivity of the composite K_{ij} , the following relation is useful (5,12)

$$K_{ij} \langle T_{,j}^t \rangle = K_{ij}^m \langle T_{,j}^t \rangle + \frac{1}{V_D} (K_{ij}^f - K_{ij}^m) \int_{\Omega} T_{,j}^t dv \quad (21)$$

where

$$\langle T_{,i}^t \rangle = T_{,i}^o + \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} T_{,i}^* dv \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{,i}^t &= T_{,i}^o + \tilde{T}_{,i} + T_{,i}^c \\ &= T_{,i}^o + S_{ij} T_{,j}^* - \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} (T_{,i}^c - T_{,i}^*) dv \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

and where T^t is the total (actual) temperature and $\langle \rangle$ denotes the quantity averaged over the entire composite D .

From Eqs. (17), (20), and (21), we obtain the thermal conductivity of an aligned short-fiber composite as

$$K_{\underline{ij}} = K^m + \frac{f(K^f - K^m)K^m}{(K^f - K^m)(1-f)S_{\underline{ij}} + K^m} \quad (24)$$

where the repeated indices with underline are not to be summed.

2.5. Misoriented Short-Fiber Composites

As we have discussed in the previous section, there exists a complete analogy between steady-state heat conduction and elasticity as far as the equivalent inclusion method is concerned. Thus, it is worthwhile to review the previous works on the effective elastic stiffness of a misoriented short-fiber composite. The case of a completely random short-fiber composite was studied by Takahashi and his co-workers (16,17) and Chou and Nomura (11), whereas, the case of two-dimensionally (2-D MSFC) and three-dimensionally misoriented short-fiber composites (3-D MSFC) was treated by Takao and his co-workers (18,19) who used two types of distribution functions of the fiber orientation, uniform and cosine type. Thus, the model used by Takao et al. has dealt with more generalized cases of fiber misorientation and will be used in this paper.

Let us consider an infinite matrix with thermal conductivity K_{ij}^m containing three-dimensionally misoriented short fibers (Ω) with thermal conductivity K_{ij}^f as shown in Figure 2(a). The entire composite body D is subjected to the uniform applied heat flux q_i^0 which is set to coincide the x_i -axis of the global coordinates x_1, x_2 and x_3 . Now a single fiber is introduced into the composite D . The orientation of this fiber is defined by angle θ and ϕ as shown in Figure 2(b), where the local coordinates x_1', x_2' and x_3' were used to describe this fiber, and the x_3' axis was set to coincide with the fiber axis (see also Figure 2(c)). Then, the equivalent inclusion method for this representative fiber (Ω) yields

$$\begin{aligned} q_i^{0'} + q_i' &= K_{ij}^m (T_{,j}^{0'} + \tilde{T}_{,j}' + T_{,j}^{C'} - T_{,j}^{*'}) \\ &= K_{ij}^f (T_{,j}^{0'} + \tilde{T}_{,j}' + T_{,j}^{C'}) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

and

$$T_{,i}^{C'} = S_{ij} T_{,j}^{*'} \quad (26)$$

where the prime indicates the quantity referred to the local coordinate system. Since the added single fiber can be regarded as a representative fiber in the composite, Eqs. (25) and (26) hold for any fiber in the matrix. From Eqs. (25) and (26), $T_{,i}^{*'}$ is easily solved as

$$T_{,i}^{*'} = (K_{ij}^m - K_{ij}^f) A_{jk}^{-1} (T_{,k}^{0'} + \tilde{T}_{,k}') \quad (27)$$

where A_{jk}^{-1} is the inverse of A_{jk} given by

$$A_{jk} = (K_{j\ell}^f - K_{j\ell}^m) S_{\ell k} + K_{jk}^m \quad (28)$$

By eliminating $T_{,i}^{*'}$ from Eqs. (26) and (27), we obtain

$$T_{,i}^{C'} = S_{ij} (K_{jk}^m - K_{jk}^f) A_{k\ell}^{-1} (T_{,\ell}^{0'} + T_{,\ell}'). \quad (29)$$

Let us introduce a transformation tensor X_{ij} defined by

$$y_i = X_{ij} y_j' \quad (30)$$

where y_i and y_j' are the components of a vector y in the global and local coordinates, respectively. Then, $T_{,i}^*$ and $T_{,i}^c$ are obtained as

$$T_{,i}^* = X_{ij} (K_{jk}^m \delta_{jk} - K_{jk}^f) A_{kl}^{-1} X_{ln}^{-1} (T_{,n}^o + \tilde{T}_{,n}) \quad (31)$$

$$T_{,i}^c = X_{ij} S_{jkl} (K_{kl}^m \delta_{kl} - K_{kl}^f) A_{ln}^{-1} X_{np}^{-1} (T_{,p}^o + \tilde{T}_{,p}) \quad (32)$$

where X_{ln}^{-1} is the inverse of X_{ln} .

A substitution of Eqs. (31) and (32) into Eq. (19) yields the solution of $\tilde{T}_{,i}$. Then, inserting $\tilde{T}_{,i}$ into Eq. (31) and the resulting equation into Eqs. (21)-(23), we obtain the thermal conductivity of a misoriented short-fiber composite. In some of the above equations, integration with respect to θ and ϕ must be performed. This will be explained below.

For example, $\langle T_{,i}^* \rangle_{\Omega}$ can be

$$\langle T_{,i}^* \rangle_{\Omega} = \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} T_{,i}^* dv = \frac{1}{V_D} \int_0^{\alpha} \int_0^{2\pi} T_{,i}^*(\theta, \phi) \rho(\theta, \phi) V ds \quad (33)$$

where $\rho(\theta, \phi)$ is the number of fibers intersecting a unit area of the unit sphere (Figure 2(c)), V is the volume of the fiber, $ds = \sin \theta d\theta d\phi$ and $T_{,i}^*(\theta, \phi)$ is a function of θ and ϕ through X_{ij} . The volume fraction of fibers f can be defined as

$$f = \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} \rho(\theta, \phi) V ds \quad (34)$$

With Eq. (34), Eq. (33) is reduced to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T_{,i}^* \rangle_{\Omega} &= \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} T_{,i}^* dv \\ &= f \frac{\int_0^{\alpha} \int_0^{2\pi} T_{,i}^*(\theta, \phi) \rho(\theta, \phi) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi}{\int_0^{\alpha} \int_0^{2\pi} \rho(\theta, \phi) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

In Eqs. (33) and (35), α is the limit of the fiber orientation angle θ (note that $-\alpha \leq \theta \leq \alpha$ and $0 \leq \alpha \leq \pi/2$).

Detailed closed-form solutions for several distribution functions are given in our previous paper (14).

3. Results and Discussions

In order to discuss the validity of the equivalent inclusion method, we will compute the numerical results obtained by Eq. (21) which then will be compared with those by self-consistent method and the bounded solutions

(7). Two types of short-fiber composites are investigated, particulate and misoriented short-fiber composites.

3.1. Particulate Composites

The results of the thermal conductivity K for a particulate composite based on Eq. (24) are plotted as a solid curve in Figure 4 as a function of the volume fraction of spherical particles. In the same figure are plotted the results by self-consistent method (dashed curve) and the bounded solutions (chain-dot curve) (7). The filled circles with error band are the experimental results of the thermal conductivity of copper powder (spherical particles) reinforced polyurethane elastomer (20). The self-consistent method used here is of standard type, i.e., two-phase model and its detailed formulation is given in Appendix B. A similar self-consistent method was used for prediction of elastic stiffness (21). It follows from Figure 4 that the lower bound of Nomura and Chou yields most accurate predictions, and the results by the self-consistent method tend to overestimate while the prediction by the equivalent inclusion method tends to underestimate. We note in passing that the lower-bound solution can be obtained from Eq. (21) if the interaction term $\tilde{T}_{,i}$ in Eq. (19) can be replaced by

$$\tilde{T}_{,i} = -f \left\{ 2T_{,i}^c - T_{,i}^* + S_{ii} \frac{K^f - K^m}{K^f} T_{,i}^o \right\}. \quad (36)$$

3.2. Misoriented Short-Fiber Composites

For most of the short-fiber composites, short fibers are misoriented either two-dimensionally (2-D MSFC) or three-dimensionally (3-D MSFC). Thus, any analytical model that is intended to be used for prediction of the thermal conductivity must be verified for the case of misoriented short-fiber case. To represent fiber misorientation, we have considered two types of distribution function ρ , $\rho = \rho_0$ (uniform type) and $\rho = \rho_0 \cos a\theta$ (cosine type) as shown in Figure 3(a) and (b), respectively. The limit of the fiber orientation angle θ is denoted by α (in radian) and its range is from 0 to $\pi/2$. It is noted here that the uniform type with $\alpha = \pi/2$ corresponds to a completely random short-fiber composite, the macroscopic properties of which are isotropic.

First, the numerical results (solid curve) based on the equivalent inclusions method and the bounded solutions (chain-dot curve) (11) for a three-dimensionally completely random short-fiber composite are plotted as a function of the volume fraction of fibers f in Figure 5 with the data $K^f/K^m = 20$ and the fiber aspect ratio $a_3/a_1 = 100$. Also shown in Figure 5 are the results based on a laminated plate model (dotted curve) which are computed by

$$K_{ij} = \frac{\int_0^\alpha \int_0^{2\pi} X_{ik} X_{jl} K_{kl}^{AL} \rho(\theta, \phi) \sin \theta \, d\theta d\phi}{\int_0^\alpha \int_0^{2\pi} \rho(\theta, \phi) \sin \theta \, d\theta d\phi} \quad (37)$$

where K_{kl}^{AL} is a component of the thermal conductivity of aligned short-fiber composites with all fibers with orientation angle θ and ϕ and its value was computed based on Eq. (21). The discrepancy between the solid (the

Figure 3 - Distribution functions of fiber orientation ; uniform distribution $\rho=\rho_0$ (a) and cosine type distribution $\rho=\rho_0 \cos a\theta$ (b).

Figure 4 - Comparison of the thermal conductivity for spherical particle ($\text{Cu}:K^f=398 \text{ W/mK}$) reinforced polyurethane elastomers ($K^m=0.256 \text{ W/mK}$) between experimental values and theoretical predictions.

Figure 5 - The thermal conductivity (K) of a three-dimensionally random short fiber composite as a function f .

Figure 6 - The thermal conductivity (K_{33}) of short fiber composites with various orientation distributions as a function of f .

Figure 7 - The thermal conductivity (K_{33}) of various types of misoriented short fiber composites as a function of α (degree).

present model) in Figure 5 can be considered as the interaction among various fiber orientations. It follows from Figure 5 that the results based on the equivalent inclusion method lie between the bounded solutions over a wide range of f , hence the equivalent inclusion method has proved to yield accurate prediction for the thermal conductivity of a misoriented short-fiber composite.

Then, we have conducted a parametric study to examine the effect of various parameters on the conductivity. First, the effect of fiber orientation distribution was studied and the results of K_{33}/K^m are plotted as a function of f in Figure 6 where four types of distribution functions are considered, aligned fibers (AL), two-dimensional cosine type (2-COS), two-dimensional uniform type (2-UNI), three-dimensional cosine type (3-COS), and three-dimensional uniform type (3-UNI), and α is set equal to $\pi/2$. It is noted in Figure 6 that the cases of 2-UNI and 3-UNI correspond to those of two-dimensional and three-dimensional completely random short-fiber composites, respectively, since $\alpha = \pi/2$. Next, the effect of α was investigated and the results of K_{33}/K^m are plotted in Figure 7 as a function of f for various types of distribution functions and $f = 0.4$. It follows from Figure 7 that the value of K_{33} decreases with α and this is more enhanced in the case of 3-UNI.

4. Conclusion

We have shown that the equivalent inclusion method proved to be useful in predicting the thermal conductivity of a short-fiber composite, particularly misoriented short-fiber composite. In addition to short-fiber composites, the equivalent inclusion method can be applied to other types of composites, such as three-phase composites, owing to its simplicity of solution procedure.

References

1. R. Hamilton and O. Crossor, "Thermal Conductivity of Heterogeneous Two-Component System," Ind. Eng. Chem. Fund., 1 (1962), pp. 187-191.
2. E. Beherens, "Thermal Conductivities of Composite Materials," J. Comp. Mater., 2 (4) (1968), pp. 2-17.
3. J. Ashton, J. Halpin, and P. Petit, Primer on Composite Materials: Analysis, Technomic Pub. Co., Stamford, CT, 1969.
4. L. Nielson, "Thermal Conductivity of Particulate-Filled Polymers," J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 17 (1973), pp. 3819-3820.
5. A. Rocha and A. Acrivos, "On the Effective Thermal Conductivity of Dilute Dispersions," Quartl. J. Mech. Appl. Math., 26 (1973), pp. 217-233.
6. J. R. Willis, "Bounds and Self-Consistent Estimates for the Overall Properties of Anisotropic Composites," J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 25 (1977), pp. 185-202.
7. S. Nomura and T. W. Chou, "Bounds of Effective Thermal Conductivity of Short Fiber Composites," J. Comp. Mater., 14 (1980), pp. 120-129.
8. T. Aboude, "Effective Thermoelastic Constants of Short-Fiber Composites," Fibre Sci. Tech., 20 (1984), pp. 211-225.
9. D. Polder and J. H. Van Stanten, "The Effective Permeability of Mixtures of Solids," Physica, 12 (5) (1946), pp. 257-271.
10. H. Fricke, "A Mathematical Treatment of the Electric Conductivity and Capacity of Disperse Systems," Phys. Rev., 24 (1924), pp. 575-587.
11. T. W. Chou and S. Nomura, "Fibre Orientation Effects on Thermoelastic Properties of Short Fibre Composites," Fibre Sci. Tech., 14 (1980-1981), pp. 279-291.
12. H. Hatta and M. Taya, submitted for publication.

13. J. D. Eshelby, "The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problems," Proc. Roy. Soc. London, A 241 (1957), pp. 376-396.
14. H. Hatta and M. Taya, submitted for publication.
15. T. K. Lai, "Thermal Stress Due to Disturbance of Uniform Heat Flow by an Ellipsoidal Inclusion," Ph.D. Dissertation, Northwestern University (1977).
16. K. Takahashi, K. Harakawa, K. Tanaka, and T. Sakai, "Analysis on the Effect of Filler Orientation Distribution in Elastic Reinforcement Theory," Zairyo (in Japanese), 26 (1977), pp. 1232-1237.
17. K. Takahashi, T. Ochiai, and K. Sawafuji, "Elastic Moduli of Discontinuous Carbon Fiber/Nylon-66 Composites," Proc. Japan Soc. Comp. Mat. (in Japanese), 10 (1984), pp. 71-76.
18. Y. Takao, M. Taya, and T. W. Chou, "Effective Longitudinal Young's Modulus of Two-Dimensionally Misoriented Short Fiber Composites," in Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, eds. T. Hayashi et al., ICCM-IV, Tokyo (1982), pp. 1091-1098.
19. Y. Takao, T. W. Chou, and M. Taya, "Effective Longitudinal Young's Modulus of Misoriented Short Fiber Composites," J. Appl. Mech., 49 (1982), pp. 536-540.
20. Private communication, K. Hani and T. Takei, Mitsubishi Electric Corporation, Polymer Eng. Dept., Sagami-hara, Kanagawa, Japan.
21. S. Nomura, T. W. Chou, and M. Taya, "A Self-Consistent Approach to the Elastic Stiffness of Short-Fiber Composites," J. Comp. Mater., 14 (1980), pp. 178-188.

Appendix A: Tensor S_{ij}

For an ellipsoid, S_{ij} is defined by (12)

$$S_{ij} = \frac{a_1 a_2 a_3}{4} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{x_1^2}{a_1^2+s} + \frac{x_2^2}{a_2^2+s} + \frac{x_3^2}{a_3^2+s} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta(s)} ds \quad (A-1)$$

where $\Delta(s)$ is given by

$$\Delta(s) = \sqrt{(a_1^2+s)(a_2^2+s)(a_3^2+s)} \quad (A-2)$$

Eq. (A-1) indicates

$$S_{ij} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad i \neq j. \quad (A-3)$$

Performing differentiation in Eq. (A-1), we obtain

$$S_{ii} = \frac{a_1 a_2 a_3}{2} \int_0^\infty \frac{ds}{(a_i^2+s)\Delta(s)} \quad (A-4)$$

where the repeated index i is not to be summed. This is the elliptic integral in general but can be expressible by elementary function for simple geometry of ellipsoid as follows.

(1) Sphere ($a_1 = a_2 = a_3$)

$$S_{11} = S_{22} = S_{33} = 1/3. \quad (A-5)$$

(2) Elliptic Cylinder ($a_3 \rightarrow \infty$)

$$S_{11} = \frac{a_2}{a_1 + a_2}, \quad S_{22} = \frac{a_1}{a_1 + a_2}, \quad S_{33} = 0. \quad (\text{A-6})$$

(3) Penny-shape ($a_1 = a_2 \gg a_3$)

$$S_{11} = S_{22} = \frac{\pi a_3}{4a_1}, \quad S_{33} = 1 - \frac{\pi a_3}{2a_1}. \quad (\text{A-7})$$

(4) Oblate Spheroid ($a_1 = a_2 > a_3$)

$$S_{44} = S_{22} = \frac{a_1^2 a_3}{2(a_1^2 - a_3^2)^{3/2}} \left\{ \cos^{-1} \frac{a_3}{a_1} - \frac{a_3}{a_1} \left[1 - \frac{a_3^2}{a_1^2} \right]^{1/2} \right\}, \quad (\text{A-8})$$

$$S_{33} = 2S_{22}$$

(5) Prolate Spheroid ($a_1 = a_2 < a_3$)

$$S_{11} = S_{22} = \frac{a_1^2 a_3}{2(a_3^2 - a_1^2)^{3/2}} \left\{ \frac{a_3}{a_1} \left[\frac{a_3^2}{a_1^2} - 1 \right]^{1/2} - \cosh^{-1} \frac{a_3}{a_1} \right\},$$

$$S_{33} = 1 - 2S_{22}.$$

Appendix B: Self-Consistent Method

In self-consistent method, it is assumed that a representative fiber is surrounded by homogeneous material with composite properties. Thus, equivalence condition is given by

$$K_I^C = (T_{,i}^O + T_{,i}^C, T_{,i}^* - T_{,i}^*) = K_{ij}^f (T_{,j}^O + T_{,j}^C) \quad (\text{B-1})$$

where K_I^C is anisotropic conductivity of the composite discussed in Section 2.2. By use of Eq. (13) we can solve for $T_{,i}^*$ as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T_{,i}^* &= A_{ij}^{-1} (K_{jk}^C \delta_{jk} - K_{jk}^f) T_{,k}^O \\ A_{ij} &= (K_{ik}^f - K_I^C \delta_{ik}) S_{kj}^A + K_I^C \delta_{ij} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{B-2})$$

By substituting Eq. (B-2) into (B-1), we arrive at

$$K_I^C = K^m + \frac{f K_I^C (K_{ii}^f - K^m)}{(K_{ii}^f - K_I^C) S_{ii}^A + K_I^C} \quad (\text{B-3})$$

where the lower case repeated indices i with underlining should not be summed, and S_{ii}^A is defined by Eq. (14).

To compute the thermal conductivity of the composite, K_I^C , we must use iteration method in Eq. (B-3). However, the cases of fiber being either cylinder or sphere can be solved explicitly.

For cylinder:

$$\begin{aligned} K_3^c &= (1-f)K^m + fK^f \\ K_1^c &= K^m + \frac{2fK_1^c(K^f - K^m)}{K_1^c + K^f} \end{aligned} \quad (B-4)$$

For sphere:

$$K^c = K^m + f \frac{3K^c(K^f - K^m)}{2K^c + K^f} \quad (B-5)$$

In the above equations unknowns (K_1^c and K^c) are to be solved.

